

Grain quality of some Basmati genotypes

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Grain size and shape must be considered in germplasm improvement along with milling percent because they largely determine the market acceptability of milled rice. Long, slender rice grain fetches a high price on the international market. Elongation of rice grains during cooking is one of the unique features of Basmati rice. Some of the key Basmati traits—slenderness, translucency, and aroma—are simply inherited, but linear grain elongation follows a complex pattern of inheritance. In thaladi 1995 (September-October-January-February), we evaluated 23 rice genotypes along with two checks, Taraori Basmati and Pusa Basmati, for hulling, milling, head rice recovery, breadth, length-breadth ratio (L/B), and elongation ratio for rice quality improvement. A randomized block design with three replications was used on 12-m² plots and each genotype transplanted with 20- × 15-cm spacing.

Brown rice percent among the genotypes ranged from 70.38 to 87.16% and milled rice percent ranged from 56.86 to 80.25% (see table). The highest for brown rice (87.16%) and the highest for milled rice (80.25%) were recorded for the HKR90-414 genotype. Head rice recovery ranged from 25.01 to 53.59%. The genotype RP3138-42-11-7-1 had the highest head rice recovery of 53.59%, followed by RP3121-14-70-2 (43.61%), which are higher than the check (Taraori Basmati, 27.57%). Twelve out of 23 genotypes approached the checks in kernel length and L/B. The genotypes RP3138-42-11-7-4, RP3138-78-25-11-4, and RP3138-56-11-9-3 showed more than double the grain elongation during cooking and was higher than Pusa Basmati. ■

Grain quality characteristics of some rice genotypes at TRRI, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India. 1995 thaladi.

Genotype	Brown rice (%)	Milled rice (%)	Head rice recovery (%)	Milled grain			Cooked grain length	Elongation ratio
				Length	Breadth	L/B		
UPR1071-21-1-1	81.31	73.36	41.01	6.64	1.55	4.28	10.50	1.58
RP3238-33-15-7	84.16	76.57	32.85	7.20	1.71	4.21	11.10	1.54
RP-ST-328	75.85	68.17	34.90	6.68	1.65	4.10	11.70	1.75
HKR90-421	82.54	72.95	37.13	6.93	1.64	4.22	12.30	1.77
HKR90-404	80.43	70.74	41.31	6.81	1.76	3.86	11.10	1.62
HKR90-403	84.26	79.46	25.04	6.83	1.72	3.97	13.00	1.90
HKR90-413	84.31	79.42	25.01	7.67	1.58	4.85	12.30	1.60
HKR90-414	87.16	80.25	27.61	7.73	1.62	4.77	12.00	1.55
BK843-2	80.14	56.86	25.39	7.06	1.63	4.33	11.80	1.67
BK843-7	80.55	70.66	28.69	7.30	1.62	4.51	12.50	1.71
NDR6017	82.49	73.37	41.16	6.82	1.66	4.10	11.10	1.62
HKR91-405	75.78	68.12	39.10	6.18	1.55	4.10	12.00	1.94
HKR91-406	78.12	70.41	32.45	7.91	1.74	4.55	12.90	1.63
HKR91-408	85.16	74.76	33.94	7.29	1.64	4.45	11.90	1.63
RP3138-42-11-7-1	72.97	69.34	53.59	6.92	1.69	4.09	12.30	1.77
RP3138-42-11-7-4	77.78	68.27	26.45	6.88	1.59	4.32	15.30	2.22
RP3138-78-20-9-2	80.08	70.62	29.94	6.97	1.56	4.47	12.70	1.82
RP3138-78-25-11-4	75.65	64.71	26.44	7.13	1.62	4.40	15.50	2.17
HKR92-401	84.69	75.64	33.05	7.71	1.61	4.79	12.80	1.66
RP3121-14-70-2	84.67	75.19	43.61	7.45	1.61	4.63	11.90	1.59
RP3138-56-11-9-3	78.07	67.93	26.81	6.89	1.66	4.15	14.70	2.13
RP3138-60-9-6-6	78.28	70.01	26.04	7.16	1.64	4.37	13.20	1.84
UPR-BS-92-4	78.03	66.49	26.68	7.48	1.62	4.62	13.30	1.77
Taraori Basmati	70.38	64.83	27.57	7.52	1.67	4.50	13.90	1.83
Pusa Basmati	85.18	72.17	26.06	7.64	1.64	4.66	14.50	1.89
Mean	80.33	71.53	32.47	7.15	1.64	4.31	12.60	1.76
CV	2.72	5.24	3.52	0.80	5.78	0.64	1.64	0.18

Physicochemical properties of japonica and indica waxy rice

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Waxy rice is important for dessert and sweet products. Five japonica and five indica varieties were tested during 1996 to compare their physicochemical properties. The varieties were Sinseonchalbyeo, Buklukbanna, Wonsanchalbyeo, Iri309, and Hwaseonchalbyeo (japonica) and Hankangchalbyeo, Iri352, IR29, IR65, and RD6 (indica).

Alkali spreading values at 1.7 and 1.4% KOH, protein, and Mg content were not significantly different except for amylose ($p < 0.05$), K content

($p < 0.05$), and Mg/K ($p < 0.01$) between japonica and indica milled waxy rices (see table). Hardness of japonica (9.83 kg) of cooked waxy rice was higher than that of indica (6.95 kg), but the other texturometer measurements were not different. The results indicated that the hardness of cooked waxy rice is an important eating quality indicator of japonica and indica waxy rice.

The water-binding capacity was significant between japonica and indica waxy rice starches ($p < 0.01$), 196 and 183%, respectively (see table). Gel consistency, which ranges from 78 to 88 mm, is soft and not significant between them. The transmittance and swelling power of japonica were lower and higher than those of indica waxy rice starch in the slope of the curves below 70 °C. The peak ($p < 0.05$), breakdown ($p < 0.050$), and setback ($p < 0.01$) amylograph viscosities were significantly dif-

ferent between japonica and indica waxy rice starches, whereas the pasting temperature, final at 95°C, cooled to 50°C, and consistency were not significant. The results showed the differ-

ences between breakdown and setback amylograph viscosities because indica has higher value of peak viscosity than japonica waxy rice starch. ■

Physicochemical properties of japonica and indica waxy rice. Korea, 1996.

Characteristic	Waxy rice		LSD ^c
	Japonica ^a	Indica ^b	
	<i>Milled waxy rice</i>		
Chemical property			
Amylose (%)	2.0	2.6	*
Alkali spreading value (1-7)			
1.7% KOH	6.3	6.5	ns
1.4% KOH	3.8	3.8	ns
Protein (%)	7.5	7.6	ns
Mg (ppm)	887	893	ns
K (ppm)	2,239	2,676	**
Mg/K	1.28	1.09	**
Texturogram			
Hardness (kg)	9.83	6.95	*
Adhesiveness	-1.18	-1.20	ns
Cohesiveness	0.17	0.19	ns
Springiness	0.96	0.93	ns
Gumminess	1.47	1.24	ns
Chewiness	1.40	1.19	ns
	<i>Waxy rice starch</i>		
Water-binding capacity (%)	196	183	**
Gel consistency (mm)	78(S) ^d	88(S)	ns
Transmittance (% at 625 nm)			
<70 °C	23.9-32.4	28.9-42.7	**
≤70 °C	76.3-78.4	78.2-78.8	ns
Swelling power			
<70 °C	1.4-7.7	1.33-5.1	*
≤70 °C	over 20	over 20	ns
Amylography (RVU)			
Pasting temperature (°C)	70.2	70.6	ns
Peak	273	281	*
Final at 95 °C	99	98	ns
Cooled 50 °C	135	132	ns
Breakdown	173	183	*
Setback	-138	-149	**
Consistency	35	34	ns

^aJaponica = Sinseonchalbyeo, Buklukbanna, Wonsanchalbyeo, Iri309, and Hwaseonchalbyeo. ^bIndica = Hankangchalbyeo, Iri352, IR29, IR65, and RD6. ^c*,** = significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level, respectively. ns = not significant. ^dBased on Cagampang et al (1973) = S:soft (61-100 mm).

A method of producing Basmati rice aroma from *Bassia* flowers

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The aroma of Basmati rice was identified as 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline (AP) by Buttery and colleagues, and Schieberle developed a simple method of its synthesis from proline and sugar. Our

group slightly modified this method. We reported (IRRN 17(5):9,1992) that the sweet smell of some indigenous varieties of unboiled fragrant rice was the same as that of our synthetic product, and this product, although proline-based, was different from AP. Using gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (GCMS) analysis, we tested pure AP from Schieberle's laboratory and have now established that the

fragrance of unboiled rice is the same as that of AP. We have also traced AP in the fresh flowers of *Bassia latifolia* in relatively large amounts. Because synthesis (by both Schieberle and us) is based on the Maillard reaction, it yields only microgram quantities of AP from grams of proline and sugar. For larger quantities, production of AP from *Bassia* was considered.

Paper chromatographic studies first established the *Bassia* fragrance as that of AP. We further confirmed this result using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; C18 microbondapak column, isocratic runs with methanol: water at 50:50, pump pressure 0.5 ml min⁻¹). Since we have found that AP-citrate remains stable for at least 6 mo, fresh flowers were macerated in excess citric acid, chromatographically purified, and compared with GCMS-tested standard AP, which was likewise treated with excess citric acid. Peaks for citric acid and AP-citrate were clearly visible in the standard and *Bassia* extracts. This observation may be the first one documenting the occurrence of AP in a flower. Steam distillation of *Bassia* flower and collection in pure citric acid thus yields AP-citrate that might be utilized after purification. ■

Effect of degree of polish on physical and gravimetric properties of rough rice

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Knowledge of rice's physical and gravimetric properties, such as grain size, bulk density, and porosity are important for designing systems for handling, transport, storage, drying, and other processes. Degree of polish is a most important parameter for trade purposes because milled rice quality, amount of bran, and oil content depend on it. This study determined the pro-